

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE METHOD OF DEVELOPING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation In this paper, the author introduces the developed complex of outdoor games, which created favorable conditions for fixing the basic program material, the main types of movements. A comparative analysis of the results of the conducted pilot study was carried out.

Key words: preschool education, physical development, need, pedagogical influence, research, exercises, abilities.

In this paragraph, we describe the experimental work carried out in the preschool educational institution on the problem of the development of the physical qualities of preschoolers in the process of physical fitness, but for this, at the beginning, we pay attention to the health groups of each child. And then, using the research methods used in the experimental work, such as: control tests (tests), pedagogical experiment and mathematical and statistical methods, we analyze and process the data obtained, which is fully consistent with the logic of the study.

Before assigning children to a particular health group, it is necessary to study and evaluate their condition according to four main criteria: the presence or absence of diseases; level of physical and mental development, harmony of development; the level of the physical systems of the body; resistance to harmful environmental factors (including diseases).

It can be seen from the data in the table that, in general, the observed group is physically developed. The growth of preschoolers 4-5 years old ranges from 93 to 104 cm, which is close to normal. The weight of preschoolers is also normal and ranges from 17 to 23 kg.

In the group, **54%** of practically healthy children and **46%** of children with developmental deviations. **23%** of children have a posture disorder.

The most common diseases are: respiratory tract infections and gastrointestinal disorders.

Successful solution of the problems of development of physical qualities largely depends on the possibilities of timely and correct control over the preparedness of those involved. In this regard, the method of control tests carried out using various standards, samples, exercises and tests has become widespread. Their application allows teachers to determine the state of fitness among students, the level of development of physical qualities and other indicators, and ultimately allows to judge the effectiveness of the applied method of developing physical qualities. In our pedagogical research, we have identified the degree of physical condition of preschool children.

Determination of the physical condition of children with the help of physical activity.

Run

In preschool children, three types of running can be conditionally distinguished by speed: fast running, running at an average speed and slow running. These types of running have different effects on the body and are used to solve various problems of physical education of children.

Fast running is the main part of many exercises, it is widely used in games, relay races and independent activities of children. For fast running, distances from 10 to 30 m. The speed of running in children increases with age, and, accordingly, the time for running a distance decreases.

Fast running has a significant impact on the activity of the main body systems. So, the pulse rate during running increases to 130 beats / min and can reach 170-180 beats / min, but at the same time, its rapid recovery is noted: already at the 1st minute it decreases to 130-140 beats / min and at 2- 3rd min returns to the original level. In order to develop speed, speed-strength qualities and increase the functionality of children, fast running is combined with other movements, repeated in a game or relay race 4-5 times after a short break.

Running at an average speed is the most important means of educating general endurance in preschoolers. The speed of such a run is 50-60% of the maximum running speed for children of each age. In the middle group, it ranges from 2.0 to 2.2 m/s, in the senior group - from 2.2 to 2.4 m/s, in the preparatory group - from 2.4 to 2.7 m/ s .

A long run at an average speed requires a significant increase in oxygen delivery to working muscles and organs, which enhances lung function and increases blood flow. The pulse rate for the first 30 seconds rises to 160 beats/min and during running it ranges from 160 to 170 beats/min. The duration of such a run is ensured by the fact that in the process of it there is a constant alternation of tension and relaxation of the muscles, the restoration of their performance.

Slow running is also an important means of developing endurance in children. Physical activity during slow running is less intense. The pulse rate during running increases to 135-145 beats / min. The activity of the respiratory and cardiovascular systems fully meets the needs of the body for the delivery of oxygen directly in the process of running itself.

The educator, doctor, nurse, observing the children during classes, note the presence of external signs of fatigue and the degree of their severity (Table 2).

Table 2

External signs fatigue

Observed signs and condition of the child	Degree expressiveness fatigue	
	small	Medium
Coloring skin face , neck	Slight redness of the face, calm expression	Significant redness of the face, tense expression
sweating	Minor	Expressed sweating faces

Breath	Some rapid	Sharp rapid
movements	Cheerful , tasks performed clearly	Uncertain, fuzzy, additional movements appear. Some children have motor excitation, others have retardation
well-being	Good , complaints No	Complaints of fatigue, refusal to continue tasks

With pronounced, unacceptable fatigue, all signs appear strongly. In this case, the teacher should make changes to the lesson plan: limit the load for children with moderate and pronounced signs of fatigue, reduce the number of repetitions of exercises, exclude more difficult ones, lengthen rest, etc. If pronounced signs of fatigue are observed in most children, then the content of the lesson does not correspond to the level of physical fitness of children and it is necessary to restructure it.

It should be borne in mind that in preschool children, functional changes are determined not only by the volume and intensity of muscle activity, but also by the form of physical exercises, as well as the emotional mood of children. Positive emotions reduce fatigue, with intense activity, attention does not dissipate, enthusiasm appears. However, it should be remembered that a preschooler is characterized by increased excitability, so even positive emotions should not be excessive: it is necessary to alternate exercises that increase emotional tone and exercises that require attention.

When exercising control, it is necessary to ensure that when performing exercises, the teacher pays attention to the education of correct posture and the formation of the arch of the foot.

Movements such as walking, running, climbing, etc., if performed correctly, contribute to the formation of correct posture. A number of exercises are specifically used for this purpose: exercises for the muscles of the shoulder girdle, back and abdomen. The development and strengthening of these muscle groups, mainly extensor muscles, contribute to the creation of the so-called "muscle corset", the development of correct posture. Each lesson offers exercises to develop and strengthen the arch of the foot (walking on toes, heels, climbing stairs, walking on a reduced footprint, running, etc.), but all these exercises must be performed methodically correctly.

When performing physical exercises, children should be taught to breathe correctly, this is especially important during outdoor activities. Deep breathing naturally appears in the process of performing various physical exercises. At rest, preschoolers breathe more superficially (this is due to the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the respiratory organs), therefore, oxygen delivery to organs and tissues is less. With systematic training, a stereotype is developed that provides the correct, rhythmic combination of deep breathing with movements. During outdoor activities, children should be taught to breathe through the nose, mouth, and to combine breathing with movement.

In the cold season (especially in winter), more attention should be paid to nasal breathing, especially in groups of children who have not previously been tempered. But at the same time,

one should not be afraid when, when running, walking or doing other exercises with voluntary breathing, children breathe through their mouths. As a rule, breathing through the mouth alternates with nasal breathing (if the child's nose is cleared of mucus), and the flow of cold air is replaced by warm, warmed and purified air passing through the nasal passages. This is a good tempering agent. Gradually, in the process of training, children develop rhythmic and deep breathing; they breathe not only through the mouth, but also through the nose, and the efficiency of nasal breathing increases.

The physical fitness of children was assessed according to the following parameters: running 10 m from the start (s), running 30 m from the start (s), shuttle run (s), jump from a place (cm), running jump (cm), the number of squats in 30 s.

To evaluate the test results, an assessment scale of physical fitness was used - Table 3.

Table 3 - Estimated scale physical training

Age , years , month	Level physical training				
	higher	higher Wednesday	average	below Wednesday	short
	100% and above	85- 99%	70- 84%	51-69%	50% and below
	5 points	4 points	3 points	2 points	1 point
pull up boys					
6.0-6.5	3 and above	2	1.5	1	0
6.6-6.11	4 and above	3	2	1	0.5 and below
7.0-7.5 _	4 and above	3	4	1.5 _	1 and below
Torso lift in sec , times in 30 sec Girls					
6.0-6.5	24 and above	20- 23	16- 19	10-15	9 and below
6.6-6.11	25 and above	21- 24	16- 20	11--15	10 and below

7.5	7.0- and up	28	23- 27	18- 22	12-- 17	11 and below
Standing Long Jump (cm) Girls						
6.5	6.0- and above	110	99- 109	88- 98	74- 87	73 and below
6.11	6.6- and above	120	109- 119	98- 108	84- 97	83 and below
7.5	7.0- and above	123	111- 122	99- 110	81- 98	90 and below
Standing Long Jump (cm) Boys						
6.5	6.0- and above	122	109- 121	96- 108	80- 95	79 and below
6.11	6.6- and above	128	115- 127	102- 114	86- 101	85 and below
7.5	7.0- and above	130	117- 129	104- 116	88- 103	87 and below

The result of control tests before the start of the pedagogical experiment in the control and experimental groups

Visually, the results of the study in the experimental group can be presented in the form of diagrams. The diagram shows the indicators of the jumping up of the subjects.

Diagram 1.

To identify the effectiveness of the development of physical qualities of preschoolers in both groups, after a two-month general preparatory period, control testing is carried out, with the help of which it is supposed to identify the level of development of physical qualities of preschoolers in the control and experimental

Table 6 - Comparative indicators of the development of physical qualities of preschoolers

Groups	experimental		control			
	Before	After	increase	Before	After	increase
Tests	exp .	exp .		exp .	exp .	
Standing high jump	4.9	9.25	.5	5.9	6.9	
	.6	.6		.9	.9	

According to the results of the calculations, there is a trend towards an increase in the development of the physical qualities of preschoolers in both groups, however, in the experimental group, in all three tests, the growth in the physical qualities of preschoolers is much higher in percentage terms. Individual indicators of the increase in the development of physical qualities of preschoolers according to the results of the test for measuring strength.

Individual indicators of the increase in the development of physical qualities of preschoolers according to the results of the test that determines the coefficient of endurance.

Therefore, the differences between the arithmetic mean values obtained in the experiment are considered reliable, which means that there are enough grounds to say that the experimental

method for the development of physical qualities turned out to be more effective than the other one used by the control group.

Thus, we can say that mobile, story games-exercises are an important activity in the development of physical qualities in children of preschool groups.

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